

ON THE VIBRATION OF COMPOSITE BAR IN PLAN MOTION

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SUMMARY : This paper presents the vibration analysis of the dynamic behavior of the composite structure. The mathematical model is realised using both the Hamilton's variational principle and some of the fundamental theorems of classical mechanics (the theorem of the impulse derivative and kinetic moment). Successively applying the Laplace transform and the sinuses and cosinuses finite Fourier transforms to the considered mathematical model, the dynamic response is obtained. This dynamical answer is numerical solved by taking account of studied base as a kinetic element of the mechanism. Experimental analysis of vibrations realised on the real model made possible this data's comparing with theoretical results. The analytical process presented in the paper could be extended for the other dynamical composite structures too; the errors covering the interval of 5-10%

KEYWORDS : vibrations analysis, mathematical model, transversal deformation

INTRODUCTION

The vibration analysis has become one of the most important parameters to be considered during the machines designing process, especially in the case of high velocities. The dynamic stability represents an important factor in the analysis of mechanisms presenting flexible elements.

The use of the composite materials that possess high resistance and low specific weight, represents a solution to the above mentioned problems. Also, the use of composite materials in the field of industrial robots improves their precision.

THE DETERMINATION OF THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The composite bar depending on the rapport between length and width, can be considered as Euler-Bernoulli or Timoshenko bars. In this paper, the mathematical model implies next simplifying hypothesis [1]:

- on the outside surface of the bar, there are no distributed forces and external torques;
- during the movement, no supplementary contact points or other shock generator factors will appear;
- the initial shape of the bar is considered not to be tensioned;
- the considered section will remain plane, but it doesn't keep the perpendicularity on the bar neuter axe;

Even if the considered section presents deviations from the initial shape, this study will consider that these are small enough not to be taken into consideration, the same assumptions being valid in the case of stress and deformation distribution.

The mathematical model is realised using both the Hamilton's variational principle and some of the fundamental theorems of classical mechanics (the theorem of the impulse derivative and momentum).

Considering the same hypothesis, the study will take into consideration the influence of inertial parameters over the section rotation and the influence of the cutting force. In the same time the nonuniformities of the tangential mechanical stress will not be considered.

The mathematical model for composite bars which is in plan motion and present constant section A, is described by the equation Equ1 [2]:

$$[E]\{\ddot{q}\} + [G]\{\dot{q}\} + [L]\{q\} + [V]\{q\}_{,11} = \{H\} \quad (1)$$

where:

$\{q\}$ represents the column matrix of the system output (spatial deformations) with the elements:

$$\{q\} = \{u_1; u_2; \mathbf{q}_{3,1}\},$$

\mathbf{q}_b is the rotation of the section;

u_1, u_2 are the longitudinal and transversal displacements of the bar's section;

\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{e} are the angular velocity and the angular acceleration of the bar;

E, G are the Young and Coulomb modules ;

I is the moment of inertia;

\mathbf{r} is the density;

p_1, p_2, m_3 are the loads and moment per unit length;

a_{01}, a_{02} are the components of the acceleration of the moving frame of reference;

For the simplification of the writing, it is written down [3] :

$$\{q\}_{,11} = \frac{\partial^2 \{q\}}{\partial x^2};$$

$$\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle = \iint_S \mathbf{r} ds; \quad \langle \mathbf{rI}_3 \rangle = \iint_S x_2^2 \mathbf{r} ds; \quad \langle \mathbf{AG}_2 \rangle = \iint_S G ds; \quad \langle \mathbf{EA} \rangle = \iint_S E ds; \quad \langle \mathbf{EI}_3 \rangle = \iint_S x_2^2 E ds;$$

x is the rectangular coordinate along the composite bar;

L is the length of the bar.

The [E],[G],[L] and [V] matrices depend on the elastic and dimensional characteristics of the section and they also depend on bar roto-translation elements. The [H] matrix includes the external solicitations and the inertial forces which influence the bar.

$$[E] = \begin{bmatrix} \langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle & 0 \\ 0 & -\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle & \langle \mathbf{rI}_3 \rangle \end{bmatrix} \text{ contains the masic elements of the bar's section;}$$

[G] has the elements depending of the Coriolis forces which operate in the section;

[L] contains the effects of the rotation motion and the nonuniformities of the stress from the bar's section;

$$[G] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -2\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{w} & 0 \\ 2\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{w} & 0 & 0 \\ -2\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{w} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad [L] = \begin{bmatrix} -\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{w}^2 & -\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{e} & 0 \\ \langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{e} & -\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{w}^2 & \langle \mathbf{AG}_2 \rangle \\ -\langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{e} & \langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle \mathbf{w}^2 & -\langle \mathbf{rI}_3 \rangle \mathbf{w}^2 \end{bmatrix};$$

[V] is the rigidity matrix of the composite bar's section and {H} is the matrix of external and inertial forces which operate on the bar:

$$[V] = \begin{bmatrix} -\langle \mathbf{EA} \rangle & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\langle \mathbf{AG}_2 \rangle & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\langle \mathbf{EI}_3 \rangle \end{bmatrix}; \quad \{H\} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} p_1 - \langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle (a_{01} - \mathbf{w}^2 x_1) \\ p_2 - \langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle (a_{02} - \mathbf{e} x_1) \\ m_{3,1} - p_2 + \langle \mathbf{rA} \rangle (a_{02} - \mathbf{e} x_1) \end{array} \right\};$$

The solution of the mathematical model is made in the folowing hypotheses, which are valids for the time range of the study :

- the elements of composite bar's rototranslation are constants;
- the deformations and the accelerations of the bar at the extremitis are nulls :

$$\{q\} \Big|_{x_1=0} = \{q\} \Big|_{x_1=L} = \{0\};$$

$$\{q\}_{,11} \Big|_{x_1=0} = \{q\}_{,11} \Big|_{x_1=L} = \{0\}.$$

The dynamic response is obtained using the Laplace transform and the sinuses finite Fourier transform of the spatial variable; its form is given by Equ 2 :

$$\{q\} = \frac{2}{L} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} L^{-1} \left\{ [s^2 [E] + s[G] + [L] - \mathbf{a}_n^2 [V]]^{-1} \left\{ \overline{\{H\}}^* + [E] \{s\} \{q_0\}^* + \{q_1\}^* \right\} + [G] \{q_0\}^* \right\} \cdot \sin \frac{n\mathbf{p}x_1}{L} \quad (2)$$

were: s is the complex variable Laplace ;

$\overline{\{H\}}$ is the Laplace transform of the {H} matrix;

$\{q\}^*$ is the sinuses finite Fourier transform of the {q} expression;

L^{-1} means that the function is a Laplace transform .

The initial conditions are :

$$\{q\} \Big|_{t=0} = \{q_0\}; \quad \{\dot{q}\} \Big|_{t=0} = \{q_1\};$$

The numerical results are obtained for a length composite bar $L=0.45\text{m}$, which is distributed in a mechanism, having the conduction element with the length 0.038m , that is rotating with constant angular velocity $\boldsymbol{w}=25\boldsymbol{p}(s^{-1})$.

The composite bar with the transversal rectangular section $0.005\times 0.012[\text{m}\times\text{m}]$, has an epoxidic resin matrix, reinforced with glass fibers in a longitudinal way, having a 50% the volumic percentage of the reinforced.

For this bar, the dynamic response-Equ2, may be descomposed, considering the initial conditions nulls, in two terms : the longitudinal displacement and the transversal displacement ,the both being due to the rotation movement of the bar.

The expressions of these displacements are :

$$u_1(x_1, t) = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \boldsymbol{w}^2(t)}{\boldsymbol{a}_n \boldsymbol{w}_{1n} \boldsymbol{w}_{2n} (\boldsymbol{w}_{1n}^2 - \boldsymbol{w}_{2n}^2)} \left[\frac{\boldsymbol{w}_{1n}}{\boldsymbol{w}_{2n}} (\boldsymbol{w}^2(t) - \boldsymbol{w}_n^2 - 4\boldsymbol{w}^2(t)K(t) + \boldsymbol{w}_{1n}^2)(1 - \cos(\boldsymbol{w}_{2n}t)) - \frac{\boldsymbol{w}_{2n}}{\boldsymbol{w}_{1n}} (\boldsymbol{w}^2(t) - \boldsymbol{w}_n^2 - 4\boldsymbol{w}^2(t)K(t) + \boldsymbol{w}_{2n}^2)(1 - \cos(\boldsymbol{w}_{1n}t)) \right] \sin \frac{n\boldsymbol{p}x_1}{L}; \quad (3)$$

$$u_2(x_1, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{K(n)(-1)^n \boldsymbol{w}^2(t)}{\boldsymbol{a}_n (\boldsymbol{w}_{1n}^2 - \boldsymbol{w}_{2n}^2)} \left[\frac{\sin(\boldsymbol{w}_{2n}t)}{\boldsymbol{w}_{2n}} - \frac{\sin(\boldsymbol{w}_{1n}t)}{\boldsymbol{w}_{1n}} \right] \sin \frac{n\boldsymbol{p}x_1}{L}; \quad (4)$$

in which it is note :

$\boldsymbol{w}_n = \boldsymbol{a}_n \sqrt{\frac{\langle EA \rangle}{\langle \boldsymbol{rA} \rangle}}$, is the range of the pulsations of the longitudinal vibrations ;

$\Omega_n = \boldsymbol{a}_n^2 \sqrt{\frac{\langle EI_3 \rangle}{\langle \boldsymbol{rA} \rangle - \langle \boldsymbol{r}_3 \rangle \boldsymbol{a}_n^2}}$, is the range of the pulsations of the transversal vibrations ;

$$\boldsymbol{a}_n = \frac{n\boldsymbol{p}}{L}; K(n) = \frac{\langle \boldsymbol{r}_3 \rangle}{\langle \boldsymbol{rA} \rangle - \langle \boldsymbol{r}_3 \rangle \boldsymbol{a}_n^2}; \quad \boldsymbol{w}_{1n} = \sqrt{A_n + \sqrt{A_n^2 - B_n}}; \quad \boldsymbol{w}_{2n} = \sqrt{A_n - \sqrt{A_n^2 - B_n}};$$

$$A_n = \frac{1}{2} (\Omega_n^2 - \boldsymbol{w}_n^2 - 2\boldsymbol{w}^2(t) + 4\boldsymbol{w}^2(t)K(n)); \quad B_n = (\Omega_n^2 - \boldsymbol{w}^2(t))(\boldsymbol{w}_n^2 - \boldsymbol{w}^2(t));$$

Analysing the Equ3, we observe the fact that the longitudinal displacement contains two terms. The first one is free time dependent and corresponds to a static deformation. The second one is the real vibration of the bar and it is superposed to the first term.

Fig 1 represents the variation of the transversal deformation $u(t)$, in the middle of the bar, between a time period of $0 \dots 5\text{s}$ and initials conditions nulls, resulting from a numerical solution.

Fig .1: The variation of the transversal deformation $u(t)$, in the middle of the bar (numerical solution).

The experimental treatment [4] are made with a BK2515 vibration analyser, the measures being in the time mode (0,...12.5s) and in the frequency mode , in the interval 0...1000Hz.

The mechanical signal “displacement” was processed by the piezo-electrical transductor type 4391 with the sensibility $1+0.02 \text{ pC/ms}$ and to unload the memory are used the software BK 7616 and the interface functions IEEE-488.

Was registered the displacement because these allow to compare the amplitude of the registered vibrations and the amplitude of the theoretical response.

Fig. 2 present the transversal vibrations measured in the same point like the theoretical application.

Fig .2: The variation of the transversal deformation $u(t)$, in the middle of the bar (experimental reply).

CONCLUSIONS

The theoretical results and their comparing with the experimental measured one, it shows the next conclusions :

- The pulse of the longitudinal vibrations depend only on the reinforced proportion.
- The pulses of the transversal vibrations depend both on the reinforced proportion and on its spatial distribution in the bar section. So, if we change reinforced distribution in the section, the pulses of transversal vibration can be modified.
- The pulses of the transversal, increase with the reinforced proportion.
- The pulses of longitudinal vibrations, have very big values.
- The dynamic response, measured with a BK 2515 vibration analyser, is in concordance with the one deduced analytically; the errors covering the interval of 0...10%.

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